

D2.3 COcyber roadmap and activity report

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Abstract

This deliverable presents the COcyber roadmap and activity implementation for the first project year, highlighting the coordination role and key achievements of the COcyber Secretariat. It outlines the processes established for governance, community engagement, and event planning, and details the Secretariat's support in launching the first project activities. These included three high-impact events focused on capacity building, best practice validation, and research dissemination. The Secretariat's efforts have strengthened internal coordination, advanced stakeholder engagement, and ensured

alignment with COcyber’s strategic and policy objectives, laying a solid foundation for the COcyber’s Community continued growth and impact.

Keywords

COcyber Community, Roadmap, Timeline, Secretariat, COcyber activities

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*** Deliverable types:**

R: document, report (excluding periodic and final reports).

DEM: demonstrator, pilot, prototype, plan designs.

DEC: websites, patent filings, press and media actions, videos, etc.

OTHER: software, technical diagrams, etc.

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Abbreviations

Abbreviation	Description
AI	Artificial Intelligence
AMETIC	Asociacion Multisectorial De Empresas De La Electronica, Las Tecnologias De La Informacion Y La Comunicacion, De Las Tele - COcyber partner leading synergies (WP6).
AUS	AUSTRALO marketing lab, COcyber partner leading communication, dissemination and stakeholder engagement (WP5).
CCIS	Chamber Of Commerce And Industry Of Slovenia - COcyber partner.
DEP	Digital Europe Programme, funding instrument of the European Union.
EC	The European Commission, the European public authority funding the COcyber project.
ECC	The European Cybersecurity Competence Centre, the funding authority of the COcyber project.
EITD	EIT DIGITAL, COcyber coordinator leading project management (WP1)
EOS	The European Organisation for Security, COcyber partner leading Coordination activities between cybersecurity civilian and defence spheres (WP2).
INFOBALT	Asociacija Infobalt - COcyber partner.
IVSZ	Informatikai, Tavkozlesi Es Elektronikai Vallalkozasok Szovetsege - COcyber partner.
LC	The Lisbon Council, COcyber partner leading Cybersecurity Observatory & COcyber Platform (WP3).
ULB	Université Libre de Bruxelles Solvay Brussels School, COcyber partner leading Know-how, good practice sharing, and information transfer activities (WP4).
WP	Work Package, from the COcyber working process.

Executive Summary

Deliverable 2.3 *COcyber Roadmap and Activity Report*, outlines the strategic roadmap and the implementation of COcyber activities during the first project year, with a particular focus on the role and achievements of the COcyber Secretariat. While the initial months focused on foundational work—developing a governance framework, building the community, and defining engagement procedures—the Secretariat has since moved into a dynamic operational phase, actively coordinating, supporting, and promoting a growing range of COcyber events and outputs.

The Secretariat has played a central role in mobilising the consortium and activating the COcyber Community by establishing clear processes for activity proposals, approvals, and communications. Through the creation of dedicated communication channels, regular coordination with partners, and the promotion of tools such as the Activity Toolkit (D4.3), the Secretariat has ensured consistency, quality, and strategic alignment across all project activities.

Key achievements include the coordination of the first three successful COcyber events—in Vilnius, Brussels (online), and Bilbao. These three events each explored a different format and topic: capacity-building in critical infrastructure, validation of best practices in civil-defence cooperation, and research dissemination in advanced cryptography. These events collectively reached over 80 participants and showcased COcyber’s ability to convene diverse stakeholders across sectors and Member States.

Importantly, this deliverable outlines COcyber’s plans on how to contribute to EU policy objectives by supporting the harmonisation of cybersecurity approaches between civil and military sectors. Through the planning of policy-oriented workshops and stakeholder dialogues, COcyber provides a timeline for gaining valuable knowledge for shaping actionable recommendations that will be captured in D4.5 “Policy recommendations”.

The deliverable concludes with a forward-looking perspective: over the next 12 months, COcyber will intensify its efforts by implementing the planned activities to increase community participation, expand its geographic and stakeholder reach through strengthening partnerships and collaborations with other cybersecurity initiatives focusing on dual-use application, and reinforce its impact at national, EU, and global levels. The final version of this report, due at Month 24, will include a full impact analysis and help consolidate the long-term value and sustainability of the COcyber initiative, connected to D6.6 COcyber final sustainability plan.

1 Introduction

This deliverable, **D2.3 COcyber Roadmap and Activity Report**, presents a comprehensive account of the coordination and management activities carried out within the COcyber project in the first year of its implementation to foster collaboration between cybersecurity actors from both the civilian and defence spheres. This report outlines the establishment and ongoing work of the COcyber Secretariat, the roadmap and timeline for strategic activities, and the mechanisms designed to ensure the engagement and active participation of the COcyber Community. The deliverable also provides a forward-looking framework, including key performance indicators (KPIs), event plans, and milestones that align with the project's broader policy development objectives—particularly those derived from the PESTEL analysis presented in Deliverable D4.4.

The deliverable is structured the following way:

Section 2 discusses the governance structure of the COcyber Secretariat, outlining the roles and responsibilities of key partners involved in managing the community, starting from what was defined in D2.1 and including adjustments and the ongoing lessons learnt from the actual work of the Secretariat. **Section 3** illustrates the engagement plan, detailing the strategy for identifying and sustaining active participation from a diverse set of stakeholders across the cybersecurity landscape. **Section 4** presents the COcyber roadmap, describing its six defined phases and the timeline and objectives for supporting policy development. **Section 5** provides an overview of planned events and activities, linked to the roadmap's implementation. **Section 6** highlights past activities and achievements, drawing out key lessons learned from the initial year of the project. **Section 7** outlines an impact analysis, introducing the key performance indicators (KPIs) used to measure success, and describing methods for assessing community engagement, policy influence, and sustainability. Finally, **Section 8** concludes the deliverable, summarising the progress to date and outlining the next steps leading to the final version of the report in Month 24.

1.1 Scope of the deliverable

This deliverable covers the continuous provision of management and coordination activities for the COcyber community. The Secretariat, composed of three COcyber partners, EOS (leading WP2 - coordination activities), EITD (the COcyber project coordinator), AUS (leading WP5 - Dissemination and Communication), **deliver a report of the activities performed so far and their impact, as well a roadmap, including a timeline and KPIs, for supporting** the achievement of the project objectives.

The activities organised by the project partners and coordinated by the Secretariat target the COcyber Community, made up of stakeholders representing various target groups, spanning from cybersecurity professionals, defence representatives, policymakers, SMEs, and academia. **The objective of the COcyber Community Secretariat is to steer and**

create a solid community around the COcyber project, aligned with the project's needs, by coordinating the organisation of activities by project partners, and in parallel by keeping the stakeholders that already approached the project engaged, including the involvement of the Ambassadors and the Advisory Board members.

1.2 Related WPs, tasks and deliverables

This deliverable D2.3, continues the work carried out in task 2.1 *COcyber Secretariat & governance*, which established the secretariat and its governance for the COcyber Community. This deliverable outlines the ongoing activities engaging the community, through delivering a roadmap, timeline, and KPIs.

This deliverable will define the participation of COcyber Community members in feeding the other results of the project, notably further enhancing areas of the COcyber platform through feedback surveys in collaboration with WP3 –COcyber Community will hold surveys at key points of the development of its results to gather input from members on key topics such as policy development, cybersecurity challenges, as well as evaluate the success of the Community. Furthermore, COcyber Community members will participate to the COcyber events envisioned under WP4, help disseminate COcyber results and news under WP5, and collaborate with other projects and initiatives in accordance with WP6.

2 COcyber Secretariat

As laid out in *D2.1 COcyber Governance and Management Plan*, the COcyber Secretariat is responsible for managing the overall governance and engagement of the COcyber Community. The COcyber Secretariat is formed by the project coordinator and task leaders responsible for the external coordination activities of WP2 and 5: EITD (the Administrative Officer of the Secretariat), EOS (the Chair of the Secretariat), and AUS (the Communications Coordinator of the Secretariat). WP Leaders Lisbon Council (LC), and ULB are also part of the Secretariat on a needs-only basis, to better reflect their efforts budgeted in WP2. LC, as the partner responsible for the COcyber platform implementation, liaise with the Secretariat to implement requested changes and updates. ULB, as the academic partner and owner of the *D2.2 Needs Analysis*, supports EOS in the validation of activities to make sure they match with the recommendations established in the Deliverable, and give guidance on Research and academic-related activities.

The objective of the Secretariat is to steer and create a solid community around the COcyber project, first by coordinating the organisation of activities by all project partners, and in parallel by keeping the stakeholders that already approached the project engaged, including the involvement of the Ambassadors and the Advisory Board members.

Moreover, the Secretariat plays a proactive role in stakeholder engagement by identifying and reaching out to key actors across the EU cybersecurity ecosystem, coordinating communication campaigns, and maintaining the COcyber Community database.

The Secretariat actively seeks synergies with other EU-funded initiatives in the cybersecurity domain, particularly those with dual-use potential, such as projects focused on cybersecurity for critical infrastructure. Collaboration with these initiatives—including COcyber’s sister project, ECYBRIDGE—contributes to a mutually reinforcing ecosystem in which results are exchanged, disseminated, and integrated to enhance collective outcomes. This aligns with the overarching objectives of the project as a Coordination and Support Action. In the following year, a structured engagement framework will be introduced through formal collaboration agreements, ensuring sustained cooperation among relevant partners beyond the project lifecycle and enabling the formation of new consortia to pursue future funding opportunities in dual-use cybersecurity and related fields.

2.1 COCYBER ACTIVITY ORGANISATION FLOW

The Secretariat provides support in the creation of COcyber activities. To begin, EOS, as the chair of the secretariat, regularly invites and reminds the consortium partners to insert their envisioned events in the timeline (please see section 5 for more). This preliminary stage of the event planning helps with the management and the coordination of the activities by the Secretariat, ensuring we are on track to reach our KPIs. Then Consortium members must submit, preferably a month before the date of the event, an *Activity Proposal* following the template based on the *D4.3 Toolkit for the organisation of know-how and information-sharing activities*. Within one week of the submission of the Activity Proposal, the Secretariat goes over the Proposal and provides suggestions for improvement where needed, before EOS as chair of the Secretariat gives written approval for the organization of the activity. To streamline this process a slack channel dedicated to the Secretariat was created where the Secretariat could discuss the concept of the Activity. Then AUS, as the Communication Coordinator of the Secretariat, will promote the event to the COcyber community and all target stakeholders, as defined in deliverable 5.1 *Dissemination and Communication plan*¹. This event promotion includes an announcement under COcyber’s events-page,² a dedicated social media post and invitation email to COcyber community members with Brevo (the Customer Relationship Management (CRM) system).

Following the conclusion of the event, the Secretariat helps disseminate a survey to gather feedback from the participants to the events and blog posts covering the outcomes of the event.

¹ <https://zenodo.org/records/14732821>

² <https://cocyber.eu/events>

Figure 1 COcyber Activity Organization Flow Chart

COcyber Activity Organisation Flow Chart

2.2 Partner roles within Secretariat

CHAIR OF SECRETARIAT: EOS

Within the secretariat, each role is crafted to ensure that the community’s operations are both seamless and responsive to its evolving needs and members’ feedback. The Chair of Secretariat provides overarching leadership, coordinating tasks and ensuring that all activities align with the project objectives, including the monitoring of related KPIs. The chair is also responsible for giving written approval for the organization of a COcyber activity, once the Activity concept has been accepted by the Secretariat, to the partner organizing the event and function as primary contact for activity related exchanges, except for communication and marketing tasks.

ADMINISTRATIVE OFFICER: EITD

As the project coordinator, EITD undertakes the administrative tasks, to make sure that the project activities are aligned to the project timeline, stay within budget, and comply with regulations. These tasks include but are not limited to:

- ensuring the partner organising the activities are provided with all the necessary tools to keep records (participants list, event recording, main takeaways, etc.)

- supervising the procurement of venues and general logistic related activities, e.g., catering.
- Approving the selection of paid experts for the activities by demanding relevant documentation such as CVs and motivation.
- Providing NDAs if necessary (particularly relevant in case of closed-doors meetings with defence stakeholders).
- Providing agreements to establish collaboration with other projects or initiatives, as well to regulate data flows between project partners.
- Managing the contracting of Ambassadors and their payment.
- Managing the Advisory Board.

SECRETARIAT COMMUNICATION COORDINATOR: AUS

The Secretariat Communications Coordinator is responsible for internal and external communications of the COcyber Community. EOS initially provided the stakeholders' list and requested consent to all members for GDPR compliance. Once the members were approved, they were included in COcyber Database managed by EOS and the CRM managed by AUS. AUS is responsible for the communication with the community members – for marketing purposes, such as event invitations and follow-ups and will contact them through social media channels: LinkedIn, and BlueSky and in email campaigns ensuring that messages are clear, timely, and consistent with the community's values.

3 Engagement Plan

The COcyber Secretariat is proactively identifying and engaging relevant stakeholders from Europe and beyond within both the civil and defence cybersecurity spheres, with the aim of growing the COcyber Community and fostering collaboration. A key objective is to build a robust COcyber Community database by collecting and involving at least **1,000 stakeholders** in COcyber activities, as per proposal KPI. The COcyber Community is comprised of stakeholders spanning from National, regional, and local authorities for Cybersecurity, Private Sector actors, SMEs & Start-ups, European projects and national initiatives for cybersecurity and Defense, European institutions and agencies for cybersecurity, defence, and diplomacy, Regulatory authorities and Standardisation bodies at the national and European levels. To maintain strong community engagement, the Secretariat ensures continuous exchanges by sharing relevant results, news and events. In parallel, the Ambassador Programme establishes a dynamic network of key cybersecurity actors across EU Member States, who act as advocates for the project—amplifying its visibility and impact at national, European, and international levels.

In addition, participation to 3rd party events and exhibitions is crucial for the engagement of new members. Most of the new contacts have been made in fact thanks to the participation of relevant cybersecurity fora, such as InForum Lille and GITEX Berlin, including national strategic event such as Miltech summit, as thoroughly described in

D5.3 Dissemination and communication activities performance reports. The participation to such key initiative is key to enlarge the community and will continue in Year 2. Many opportunities for COcyber dissemination came from the Batch #1 of Ambassadors, thus highlighting their key role for the overall project impact.

The initial process for the creation of the COcyber community was based on contacting the identified stakeholders from the stakeholder map to request their approval for them to be added to the community database as a first effort to pool relevant stakeholders.

These contacts were then targeted with a communication campaign in order to finalise their registration to the COcyber platform.³ In parallel, contacts who registered directly on the COcyber platform were added to the database manually – LC providing the registration data to EOS who then checks and updates the database.

Later on, all contacts registering to the platform will be automatically included in the CRM through the Brevo API. This is an “interim” process. The final process will be all automated, meaning that the contacts in the database and the registrants to the Platform will automatically update and match and the People who register to the platform will be automatically included in the CRM.

A similar process is envisioned for the LinkedIn followers. However, as there is no way to automatically transfer the contacts, the followers of the LinkedIn page will be asked on a repeated basis to register to the COcyber platform, which will constitute the only official entry point for members who register to the COcyber Community.

The following section analyses the current composition of the COcyber Community and provides a breakdown of the contacts. The COcyber Community currently comprises a total of **263 members** drawn from a diverse set of stakeholder groups and countries, reflecting the project's aim to foster inclusive and cross-sectoral engagement in cybersecurity. The community includes **106 SME and Civil Society organizations**, making SME and Civil Society the largest stakeholder group, followed by **56 policymakers, 51 academic institutions, 40 Cybersecurity professionals, and 10 defence-related stakeholders**. Unfortunately, reaching out to defence sector has proven to be a challenge and marketing and communication campaigns will be used to target the sector in order to make up for the lack in numbers. COcyber members come from **32 different countries**, with the highest numbers from **Belgium (73 members), Italy 21 and Spain 20 members, France (15), and Germany (13)**. The presence of members from both EU Member States and associated countries strengthens the project's potential for policy harmonization and cross-border cooperation. This diversity across both stakeholder type and national affiliation is essential for shaping effective, collaborative cybersecurity policy recommendations that respond to the complex and interconnected challenges faced by Europe.

³ <https://cocyber.eu/user/register>

Within the Community, key stakeholder organisations on the civilian sector include academic institutions like VUB, AIT and Turku, policymakers from the European Commission, NATO, ENISA, EEAS, representatives from Deloitte, SentinelOne, Orange and women4cyber, as well as representatives from defence institutions such as the Belgian Ministry of Defense, Italian armed forces, defence companies such as Indra, and the Hellenic Naval Academy.

Moreover, within the COcyber Community some stakeholders are designated to a specific category based on their higher levels of expertise and engagement with the project.

- **Advisory Board Members:** they provide strategic guidance and comprise external experts, outstanding researchers, industry leaders, and key stakeholders with relevant experience in Cybersecurity. For Advisory Board composition and meeting outcomes, refer to D1.2 Project collaboration and risk management interim report.
- **COcyber Ambassadors:** they are the key stakeholders of the COcyber project, made up of high-level, trusted experts, the COcyber project and its objective. Their mission is to expand COcyber's reach, endorse its activities, produce and disseminate targeted content, foster one-to-one stakeholder engagement, and support the project's visibility and influence within European cybersecurity arenas. The Ambassador Programme, managed by AUSTRALO over a two-year period, includes three rounds of engagement, each lasting six months, with over 15 ambassadors selected to participate across the project lifecycle. Currently the first batch of 6 COcyber Ambassadors are finalising their term, and the second batch has been selected and is now in the process of being contracted.⁴

Over the next 12 months, COcyber will focus on strengthening member participation, expanding its reach, and delivering increased value to every stakeholder in the cybersecurity community through targeted activities. With the goal of growing the COcyber Community membership by 300%, focussing in particular on targeting stakeholders from the Defence sphere, the project will organize events almost on a monthly basis, both online and offline, with the goal of obtaining an average of 20 participants to each COcyber activity. As per Grant Agreement, the project aims to organize 10 high-level tech roundtables, 4 cybersecurity consultations, 10 capacity-building activities, 8 policy-oriented workshops, 8 research and innovation seminar, and 10 digital and cyber dialogues. At the time of this deliverable three COcyber events have already taken place. The first event was capacity building event in Vilnius, Lithuania organised by INFOBALT, the second event was an online consultation event organised by ULB, and the third was a Research and Innovation seminar organised by LC (please see section 6 for more).

⁴ <https://zenodo.org/records/15464573>

In order to ensure the qualitative impact of the project, the Steering Committee will prioritise quality over quantity and may reconsider the overall number of activities to be organised, in close collaboration with the PO.

In order to engage the COcyber Community the project will deploy a comprehensive mix of targeted content to complement the organisation of COcyber events. Through the website, social media channels, email campaigns, and the newsletter, Community members will be updated on the results and upcoming events of the project. Currently, three out of the eight COcyber newsletters have been published. The Newsletters are published every 4 months and present the latest project updates and results. The newsletter “Cybersphere insights” are published on the COcyber’s LinkedIn page⁵ and released on the website for open access⁶.

4 Roadmap

The COcyber project establishes a roadmap for collaboration between the civilian and defence cybersecurity communities. This roadmap guides collaborative efforts, fostering ongoing cooperation through setting out 6 distinct phases covering the start of the project to over 3 years after the project’s conclusion. The roadmap helps set up the coordination activities that will connect members and stakeholders from the cybersecurity civilian and defence communities to work together on the betterment of European coordination.

The Key objective of the roadmap is:

- To foster active and long-lasting collaboration between COcyber community members and oversee their involvement in relevant project activities.

The second half of the project (M12 – M24) will see the results of the research and planning conducted in the first half of the project, as the organization of COcyber activities increases (see section 5 for more details).

4.1 Roadmap Phases

Phase 1: Governance and Community Creation (M1–M6)

In the first phase of the project, the primary focus was on establishing a solid foundation for COcyber’s operations. This includes the creation of a comprehensive Governance and Management Plan to guide the project’s execution, ensuring that the roles and responsibilities of all partners are clearly defined. Additionally, efforts will be directed towards setting up the COcyber community by leveraging existing partner connections, fostering a collaborative environment. Aligning the policy goals of COcyber with the

⁵ www.linkedin.com/build-relation/newsletter-follow?entityUrn=7272922684982743040

⁶ <https://cocyber.eu/publications>

PESTEL (Political, Economic, Social, Technological, Environmental, and Legal) findings will ensure that the project is responsive to the broader societal and regulatory contexts, setting the stage for effective and impactful outcomes.

Phase 2: Policy Development and Stakeholder Collaboration (M7–M18)

Aligned with the due date of the policy recommendations, the second phase focuses on developing actionable policy recommendations that address the cybersecurity challenges identified in earlier phases. During this phase, COcyber is intensifying its efforts to enhance multi-stakeholder collaboration, bringing together various actors within the cybersecurity ecosystem to create robust solutions. The COcyber community will also continue to grow, with an emphasis on expanding its reach and engagement. A key activity in this phase is the COcyber Member Policy Survey published in M16 (October 2025). The target for this survey is to gather at least 50 responses from the community, providing valuable feedback for shaping the policy recommendations published in D4.5

Phase 3: Validation of COcyber Results (M13–M24)

In this phase, the project will focus on validating the results achieved so far, ensuring that the activities and outputs align with the original goals and objectives of COcyber. This will involve a variety of capacity-building activities designed to enhance the skills and knowledge of the community and stakeholders. Key activities will include organizing events using the COcyber platform, and a Community Survey on COcyber results. The Surveys will aim to address key topics such as validation of the COcyber platform as well as evaluate the engagement and success of the Community. First round of surveys to be held in September 2025 and a Second round of Surveys in February 2026 so to be able to adjust anything in the last phase of the project. The goal for this survey is to receive 50+ responses, providing critical insights that will allow the project to refine its strategies and enhance its impact moving forward.

Phase 4: Sustainability and Exploitation (M18–M24)

The focus of Phase 4 is on ensuring the long-term sustainability of the COcyber project and its activities. Strategies defined in the interim plans in D6.2 and D6.3 will be re-evaluated and refined to ensure that the project continues its relevance beyond its initial phases as it meets real-world needs. One of the key objectives will be strengthening the EU's global cybersecurity leadership, ensuring that COcyber plays a central role in shaping cybersecurity policies at the international level. Activities will include hosting events and the final conference of the project, aiming for 50+ participants. A Sustainability and Exploitation Survey will be conducted for COcyber members, gathering their insights and ensuring that the results and initiatives of the project have lasting value. A KPI for this activity is to achieve at least 50 responses, helping to guide the future sustainability strategies.

Beyond the project's termination phase 5 (M24 – M60) and phase 6 (M60 +) will take place. These phases will be a clear part of the project's sustainability plan (*D6.3 COcyber Sustainability Plan*) which will see the handover of the COcyber Community and its

secretariat to the key members and stakeholders interested in continuing the work done by the project.

Figure 2 COcyber Roadmap Phases

4.2 Policy Development Support

- Role of COcyber in policy development

The European Union has developed a robust and evolving cybersecurity framework aimed at harmonising Member States' approaches, bridging the civil–military divide, and strengthening collective responses to cyber threats. Central to this effort is the EU Cybersecurity Strategy⁷, supported by the Cyber Defence Policy⁸ and the Cyber Solidarity Act⁹, which proposes a European Cybersecurity Shield and Emergency

⁷ <https://digital-strategy.ec.europa.eu/en/policies/cybersecurity-strategy>

⁸ <https://www.consilium.europa.eu/en/policies/cyber-defence/>

⁹ <https://digital-strategy.ec.europa.eu/en/policies/cyber-solidarity>

Mechanism to counter large-scale incidents. On the civil side, key legislation—including the NIS2 Directive¹⁰, the Cybersecurity Act¹¹, and the upcoming Cyber Resilience Act¹²—sets increasingly stringent security standards across sectors and digital products. However, as cyber threats increasingly blur the lines between civil and defence domains, the EU recognises the need for integrated intelligence sharing and coordinated responses, reinforcing the importance of cross-sector collaboration to effectively detect, respond to, and prevent cascading cyber incidents.

The COcyber project steps into this gap, aligning directly with the EU's long-term policy objectives by fostering coordinated civil-defence cooperation. The goal of the COcyber Policy development is to help co-defining policy recommendations for harmonisation of actions at the Member State and European level. Its core activities strengthen resilience via better information exchange through COcyber activities that build mutual trust. These forums empower the COcyber Community to innovate together, thus supporting the growth and competitiveness of Europe's cybersecurity sector.

Based on the conclusions of the Needs Assessment in D2.2¹³ and the PESTEL Analysis carried out in D4.4, this deliverable outlines the steps that will be taken to advance the policy development that will feed the policy recommendations of D.4.5, which will aim to optimise and foster better collaboration between the civilian and defence cybersecurity communities and advance the narrative on EU and international cybersecurity cooperation with all stakeholders.

The PESTEL analysis conducted in Deliverable 4.4 reveals a deeply interconnected European cybersecurity landscape, where each dimension—political, economic, social, technological, environmental, and legal—exerts a significant and distinct influence. Politically, uneven implementation of key frameworks like the NIS2 Directive and the Cyber Resilience Act weakens the EU's unified response to cross-border threats. Economically, disparities in resources across Member States hinder access to advanced technologies, leaving less-developed regions behind in adopting innovations such as AI and quantum encryption. Social challenges, including workforce shortages and public distrust in surveillance, further complicate resilience efforts. Technological fragmentation and high lifecycle costs limit the effective deployment of dual-use technologies, while environmental concerns around data centre energy consumption and infrastructure footprint highlight the need for sustainability integration. Legally, inconsistent international alignment and enforcement hinder compliance with cybersecurity and ethical standards. To address these issues, the EU must pursue equitable investment in cutting-edge technologies, promote public-private cooperation to close workforce gaps, and embed energy-efficient practices into cybersecurity infrastructure. Additionally, it must strengthen legal frameworks governing dual-use technologies and align them with

¹⁰ <https://digital-strategy.ec.europa.eu/en/policies/nis2-directive>

¹¹ <https://digital-strategy.ec.europa.eu/en/policies/cybersecurity-act>

¹² <https://digital-strategy.ec.europa.eu/en/policies/cyber-resilience-act>

¹³ <https://zenodo.org/communities/cocyber/records?q=&l=list&p=1&s=10>

international norms to uphold ethical standards. Through instruments such as NIS2, the Cyber Resilience Act, and the European Defence Fund, the EU can advance a harmonised, sustainable, and strategically autonomous cybersecurity framework capable of meeting future challenges.

In order to address these policy issues, the project aims to organize policy-oriented events, which will allow the COcyber community composed of representatives of both the civil and defence field to feed the COcyber results, including the policy recommendations which will be developed as part of D4.5.

The COcyber roadmap, plans, and key performance indicators (KPIs) are concretely aligned with the European Union's cybersecurity policy objectives by translating strategic goals into structured phases, measurable outcomes, and community-driven actions. At the core, COcyber supports the harmonisation of cybersecurity policies and enhanced coordination between civilian and defence sectors, directly addressing the fragmentation identified in EU policy frameworks such as NIS2 and the Cyber Resilience Act. This is operationalised through activities like eight policy-oriented workshops and the publication of actionable policy recommendations in D4.5, informed by stakeholder feedback gathered via targeted surveys with a KPI of at least 50 responses. The project also advances EU objectives on multi-stakeholder engagement and cross-sector cooperation by growing the COcyber Community to over 1,000 stakeholders and organising a diverse mix of events—capacity-building workshops, research seminars, and consultations—with a target of 20 participants per event and a total of 50 COcyber activities. These efforts strengthen trust, mutual understanding, and knowledge sharing between sectors. Additionally, COcyber's sustainability and international impact are ensured through Phases 4 to 6 of the roadmap, which focus on long-term exploitation, securing at least 10 external project collaborations and 5 mentions in policy documents as KPIs. By embedding PESTEL findings and real-world needs into each activity phase, and aligning outputs with legislative priorities and the EU Cybersecurity Strategy, COcyber not only supports policy development but also reinforces Europe's strategic autonomy, resilience, and leadership in cybersecurity governance.

- Planned activities and initiatives

The project will organize eight policy-oriented workshops. These policy-oriented events will involve interactive sessions dedicated to the development, refinement, or implementation of policies related to digital transformation, cybersecurity, and technology governance. These workshops will serve as a platform to connect policymakers with other key stakeholders, fostering the exchange of insights from those with hands-on experience to inspire more effective policy outcomes. While all stakeholders are welcome to participate and share diverse perspectives, the primary target audience will be national, regional, and local authorities and agencies responsible for cybersecurity.

The policy workshops tackle 2 of the NEEDS identified in the *Deliverable 2.2 Bridging Gaps: A Raw Needs Assessment Report for Enhanced Collaboration Between Civilian and Defence Cybersecurity Spheres*: The Fragmentation of cybersecurity efforts and Uncoordinated Cybersecurity Policies.

A second NEED that will be tackled by the policy-oriented workshops is the lack of coordination between civilian and defence cybersecurity policies. At present, civilian frameworks emphasize the protection of individual privacy and data rights—chiefly framed by the General Data Protection Regulation—while defence regimes prioritize national security imperatives and military operational readiness. This dual approach risks creating loopholes where either privacy concerns or defence requirements can be overlooked. There is a need for a harmonised policy environment in which civilian and military cybersecurity objectives are aligned under a centralised governance body. Such an entity could oversee the development and implementation of unified standards, reconcile regulatory differences, and streamline approval processes for critical security technologies—ensuring that Europe speaks with one voice in safeguarding both its citizens and its collective defence capabilities.

These policy events will prioritize smaller groups of participants to encourage meaningful discussion, rather than aiming for large audiences. If organizers wish to engage a broader group, the workshop can be structured in two parts: an initial introductory session for all participants, followed by smaller group discussions (ideally no more than 15 people per group), either within the same room or across multiple rooms. The atmosphere should remain informal to foster open dialogue. The venue setup should be tailored to the specific design of the activity, with an emphasis on avoiding large, impersonal spaces during the discussion segments.

4.3 Expected Outcomes and Benefits

Through fostering open dialogue among national, regional, and local cybersecurity authorities, alongside other stakeholders, these workshops will promote the exchange of practical insights and provide feedback on national level strategies. The expected outcomes include actionable policy recommendations that feed into the EU's broader strategic goals, such as those outlined in the Cybersecurity Strategy, Cyber Defence Policy, and the Cyber Solidarity Act. Ultimately, COcyber will contribute to a more resilient and unified European cybersecurity landscape—one that supports the secure adoption of emerging technologies, enhances cross-sector cooperation, and strengthens Europe's ability to detect, deter, and respond to increasingly sophisticated cyber threats.

The COcyber Community members will benefit from being able to help shape the policy environment, improved operational coordination, and a strengthened European cybersecurity ecosystem that is both competitive and strategically autonomous.

5 Timeline

The Timeline outlining the provisional dates of the types of events the COcyber partners plan to organise will be depicted and analysed in this section.

The project KPIs demand partners to organize 10 high-level tech roundtables, 4 cybersecurity consultations, 10 capacity-building activities, 8 policy-oriented workshops, 8 research and innovation seminar, and 10 digital and cyber dialogues.

The COcyber timeline outlines a series of structured events scheduled from now until the end of the project, aimed at fostering dialogue, knowledge exchange, and policy advancement in the cybersecurity domain. Key recurring formats include online cybersecurity consultations, digital and cyber dialogues, high-level tech roundtables, and policy-oriented workshops. These events are strategically distributed across the months, beginning with a capacity building activity, a cybersecurity consultation and a cybersecurity consultation in June 2025 (please see section 6 for the more). After the summer break, the events continue with policy-oriented workshops, high-level tech round tables and capacity building events in September and October. The programme intensifies towards the end of the year with additional consultations and a roundtable in November and December. The cycle continues into 2026 with new sessions planned from January through April, including policy-oriented workshops, cyber dialogues, and high-level roundtables. The series of events culminates with the final conference in May 2026. Each event targets different aspects of stakeholder engagement and policy refinement, contributing to COcyber's broader mission of bridging the civil and defence cybersecurity sectors across Europe.

Figure 3: Timeline M12 – M18

LEGEND

- IN PERSON EVENTS
- ONLINE EVENTS

Figure 4: Timeline M19 – M24

6 Past Activities and Achievements

6.1 Overview

- Summary of past activities and initiatives

The first COcyber event was an in-person capacity building event in Vilnius, Lithuania organised by INFOBALT on the 12 June 2025.¹⁴ The event titled *Cybersecurity Capacity Building at Lithuania's Electricity Transmission System Operator, Litgrid*. The event aimed to enhance awareness and understanding of cybersecurity challenges through a collaborative, multi-sectoral approach. Focusing particularly on the Lithuanian electricity transmission system operator, Litgrid, the event featured expert presentations, a guided technical visit to Litgrid's dispatch center, and open discussions involving stakeholders from the public, private, and academic sectors. Designed to encourage dialogue and knowledge exchange, the event will blend theoretical insights with practical demonstrations, fostering mutual understanding, promoting stakeholder engagement, and inspiring joint efforts to strengthen cybersecurity in critical infrastructure environments.

The event was structured the following way:

- 10:00 – 10:20 – Baltic Synchronization with the Continental European Networks (Litgrid)
- 10:20 – 10:50 – Tour of the Dispatch Control Room (Litgrid)
- 10:50 – 11:20 – DARSIS Solution: Digital Protection in Practice (Cpartners)
- 11:20 – 11:40 – Presentation of the CyberHubs and COcyber Projects (Infobalt)
- 11:40–12:00 – A discussion on critical issues in the digital and cyber landscape among diverse stakeholders (all participants)

The event featured a diverse panel of speakers, including Donatas Matelionis, Roma Oškutienė, Darius Šoparas, Jelena Koškarova, Monika Gikaraitė, Milda Savickaitė, and Virgilijus Dirma. Key topics addressed included the growing importance of digital protection tools, the persistent cybersecurity skills gap, and the critical need for trust-based information sharing between public and private sectors. Participants gained valuable insights from Litgrid representatives and cybersecurity specialists, who highlighted practical approaches to enhancing national energy resilience and mitigating digital risks. A live demonstration of the DARSIS solution showcased how cutting-edge technologies are being applied to protect critical infrastructure under real-world conditions. The event also served as an opportunity to present the COcyber project and

¹⁴ https://www.linkedin.com/posts/cocyber-eu-project_digitalresilience-capacitybuilding-skills-gaps-activity-7341736597303767040-X518?utm_source=share&utm_medium=member_desktop&rcm=ACoAACoOu2UBRt6Yn_g6SHo9hWuACH6ZO19ESqQ

its goal of promoting structured collaboration across the cybersecurity ecosystem. Discussions underscored a shared recognition of the need to combine technical capabilities with strategic dialogue to effectively confront the rapidly evolving threat landscape.

Figure 5: INFOBALT Cybersecurity Capacity Building at Litgrid

The second COcyber activity was the Online consultation event – *Best Practice validation: Cybersecurity and Civil-Defence cooperation in the EU*, organized by the COcyber partner Université Libre de Bruxelles (ULB).¹⁵ The event took place on 13 June 2025 (M12), from 10:00 to 12:00 CET, with the goal to validate 20 shortlisted practices in cybersecurity cooperation between civilian and defence sectors across the European Union. The consultation brought together 27 participants, including COcyber Ambassadors, Advisory Board members, and external experts from related European projects.

The event was structured the following way:

10:00 – 10:10- Welcome & introduction

10:10 – 11:40 – Presentation of 20 shortlisted practices and scoring on survey

¹⁵ https://www.linkedin.com/posts/cocyber-eu-project_cybersecurity-civilian-defence-activity-7336664108760465408-IMMb?utm_source=share&utm_medium=member_desktop&rcm=ACoAACoOu2UBRt6Yn_g6SHo9hWuACH6ZO19ESqQ

11:40 – 11:55 – Discussion & reflection

11:55 – 12:00 – Summary & closing remarks

The session aimed to assess and refine a selection of 20 best practices identified for their relevance to the challenges of civil-defence cooperation. Guided by moderator Georges Ataya, the consultation adopted an interactive format, allowing participants to evaluate each practice using predefined criteria such as impact, replicability, and strategic alignment. Based on the collective scoring, ten high-impact practices will be shortlisted for further development and integration into the COcyber community platform. The session also featured a reflective segment, where participants explored emerging patterns, raised critical questions, and offered contextual insights, fostering expert-driven knowledge exchange and collaborative learning. Additionally, attendees were invited to propose new best practices for potential inclusion on the platform and were briefed on forthcoming capacity-building and networking activities planned as part of the COcyber project.

Figure 6: ULB Best Practice validation: Cybersecurity and Civil-Defence cooperation in the EU

Best practices evaluation

Your Evaluation Matters!

All proposed **best practices** can be evaluated via **Microsoft Forms**.

You will receive the link in the chat — or simply scan the **QR code on this slide** to access the form.

We kindly ask you to evaluate each practice after its description and submit the form at the end of the event!

Your input is essential for selecting the most impactful and actionable practices.
Thank you for contributing to a stronger EU cybersecurity framework!

The third COcyber event was an online Research and Innovation seminar focused on Post-quantum cryptography organised by Lisbon Council on the 17th of June. The event took place at the B Accelerator Tower in Bilbao, Spain. The objective of the event was to showcase the COcyber community's expertise and attract more high-level stakeholders to the COcyber community and platform. The event brought together 35 participants from SMEs, start-ups, and public administration.

The seminar featured Professor Federico Pintore from Trento University, who addressed several key topics related to post-quantum cryptography and quantum computing. He

discussed the impact of quantum computation on currently employed cryptosystems, the collective efforts of the research community to identify secure and efficient post-quantum schemes, and the critical deadlines associated with transitioning to these new cryptographic standards. Professor Pintore also examined the goals and motivations behind the ongoing research in the field. The presentation highlighted the latest developments in post-quantum cryptography and quantum computing, linking them to broader issues of geopolitical instability and the imperative of digital sovereignty.

The speakers at the event were Federico Pintore, Federico Iannuli, and Maria-Chiara Zaccaria.

The event was structured the following way:

17:00 – 17:10- Introduction to the professor’s presentation and the COcyber project

17:10 – 17:50-The Professor proceeded with his seminar

17:50 – 18:00- Q&A session to engage the audience and create a debate around PQC and its applications.

The event was a success as the COcyber Community and the COcyber Platform was promoted in a high-level context like the Govtech4all consortium, while they were presenting their newly developed cybersecurity framework based on post-quantum cryptography.

Figure 7: LC Research and Innovation seminar focused on Post-quantum cryptography

6.2 Lessons Learned

- Insights and best practices from past activities

The COcyber events held in June 2025 provided valuable lessons and highlighted several best practices for organising effective and impactful cybersecurity activities across varied formats and stakeholder groups. The first event, an in-person capacity-building session at Litgrid in Vilnius, demonstrated the value of combining theoretical discussions with practical, site-based learning. The integration of a technical tour, expert presentations, and an open discussion fostered active engagement and cross-sector dialogue among public, private, and academic stakeholders. Key lessons included the importance of creating space for informal exchanges to build trust, and the impact of grounding theoretical cybersecurity discussions in real-world infrastructure contexts. The second event, an online consultation hosted by ULB, used a structured, interactive format that allowed participants to score and evaluate 20 best practices related to civil-defence cooperation. The scoring system, combined with a reflection segment, proved effective in generating informed input and encouraging knowledge exchange among a diverse expert audience. This format underscored the value of using predefined evaluation criteria and incorporating participatory methodologies to foster a sense of co-ownership among participants. The third event, a research seminar on post-quantum cryptography led by Lisbon Council, effectively showcased the COcyber Community's technical depth while also broadening its visibility. The seminar's success lay in aligning high-level academic content with strategic topics such as digital sovereignty and geopolitical risk, which resonated with both public sector representatives and innovative SMEs. Conducting the event in the context of the Govetech4all consortium also helped COcyber position itself as a relevant actor in cutting-edge cybersecurity debates. Across all events, strong moderation, targeted stakeholder invitations, and clear alignment between content and COcyber's mission were essential success factors. A common lesson across the three activities was the importance of combining technical expertise with strategic messaging to strengthen engagement, while creating opportunities for dialogue, evaluation, and network-building among stakeholders.

7 Impact Analysis

The objective of the **impact analysis of the COcyber Community** is to assess the extent to which the community has contributed so far to advancing cybersecurity knowledge, policy, collaboration, and resilience within the EU and beyond.

This analysis would examine four key impact areas: knowledge exchange, policy influence, collaborative engagement, and resilience-building. Quantitative data would be collected through metrics such as the number of events held, stakeholder participation levels, platform usage statistics, and the dissemination of knowledge products like newsletters and reports. Surveys distributed post-events and after reaching milestones on the platform to the COcyber Community would capture member satisfaction, perceived value,

and suggestions for improvement. Additionally, policy tracking would identify references to COcyber in EU or national cybersecurity documents. Qualitative insights would be gathered through interviews with key stakeholders—such as Ambassadors and Advisory Board members—that assess the perceived quality of collaboration and relevance of COcyber’s activities. The analysis would also benchmark performance against the project’s KPIs, such as the number of events organised, stakeholders engaged, and policy contributions made. Furthermore, the evaluation would include an assessment of long-term sustainability by analysing member retention.

7.1 KPIs

The KPIs against which the project measures the success of the COcyber activity can be divided into 3 sections. One metric deals with the number of stakeholders and participants to events, another deals with the number of types of COcyber events, and the final deals with the successful uptake of the COcyber policy recommendations. Whilst these KPIs are very challenging to reach, in particular the average number of COcyber stakeholder involved in organised activities, the project will endeavour to achieve them.

Table 1: KPIs

KPI	Target	Status
Average no. participants per activity organised	20	27.3
No. stakeholders from both communities involved in organised activities	1000	82
No. high-level tech roundtables	10	Being planned
No. cybersecurity consultations	4	1
No. capacity-building activities	10	1
No. policy-oriented workshops	8	Being planned
No. research and innovation seminars	8	1
No. digital and cyber dialogues	10	Being planned
No. Of COcyber events	50	3
No. mentions about the project and its recommendations in policy documents	5	In progress

In the second half of the project the majority of the COcyber events will take place, allowing the project to reach its KPIs.

7.2 Assessing community engagement

In order to assess community engagement, feedback will be collected through various means.

A key data source will be regular **post event surveys**.¹⁶ These surveys, disseminated to the participants post events will help gauge satisfaction levels and assess whether the community is meeting members' expectations. These post event surveys will be launched as Microsoft forms and will comprise of eight questions assessing the participants' view of the event.

Another source to assess community engagement will be the more comprehensive and in-depth **Community Survey on COcyber results** developed on the COcyber platform that will aim to address key topics such as validation of the COcyber platform as well as evaluate the engagement and success of the Community. The survey will be disseminated in two rounds. The first round of surveys to be held in **September 2025** and a Second round of Surveys in **February 2026** so to be able to adjust anything in the last phase of the project. The goal for this survey is to receive 50+ responses, providing critical insights that will allow the project to refine its strategies and enhance its impact moving forward.

Another metric to analyse the community engagement would be tracking how many members participate to events, which will be accomplished through the participation lists that will be filled in at the COcyber events.

A third metric, once the policy recommendations have been published, will be through the scanning of policy documents for mentions of COcyber and its recommendations.

The final version of the COcyber Roadmap and Activity report, that will be published in M24, will include an analysis of inactive members to gain an understanding of the reasons for their inactivity and clarify their expectations and needs from the platform. The results of the analysis of "inactive" members will result in the altering of future engagement strategies, in order to propose and develop community activities, content, and branding that will help improve user engagement. The final version of this report will also include sections discussing the broader influence and legacy of the COcyber project. Section 7.4 *Impact of knowledge sharing and collaboration* will assess the Section 7.3 on *Policy and Advocacy Influence of the COcyber Community* will document the number and type of policy briefs, recommendations, and advocacy documents produced, as well as their uptake by decision-makers—such as whether they were presented to EU institutions or influenced legislation. This section will also evaluate stakeholder engagement through metrics like meetings with EU officials and cybersecurity industry leaders to assess COcyber's role in shaping policy discourse. Section 7.4 on *Sustainability and Long-Term Impact* will focus on the durability of COcyber's initiatives beyond the project lifecycle, using indicators like community retention, stakeholder feedback, and the continued relevance and use of project outputs. Lastly, Section 7.5 on *COcyber's Contribution to EU*

¹⁶ <https://forms.office.com/e/J1PLRDyYEn>

and *Global Cybersecurity Leadership* will assess the project's international visibility and its alignment with EU strategic objectives. This includes COcyber's participation in global cybersecurity dialogues and its potential role in enhancing the EU's influence in shaping cybersecurity norms and policies worldwide.

8 Conclusions

The D2.3 COcyber Roadmap and Activity Report marks a significant milestone in the project's efforts to coordinate and integrate cybersecurity communities across Europe's civilian and defence sectors. This deliverable has laid out a structured, phased roadmap supported by a robust governance framework, stakeholder engagement strategy, and a clear timeline of activities. It has also introduced key performance indicators to monitor progress, foster accountability, and guide the Secretariat and partners in achieving the project's strategic objectives.

The Secretariat has successfully coordinated the planning of COcyber activities, supported by engagement mechanisms such as the Ambassador Programme, the COcyber Community database, and diverse policy-oriented and technical events. Through these mechanisms, COcyber has cultivated a growing and diverse community, reflecting the project's commitment to inclusiveness, cross-border collaboration, and policy relevance. The roadmap phases, from foundation to long-term sustainability, reflect a clear vision to evolve COcyber into a long-lasting actor in the European cybersecurity landscape.

As COcyber enters the second half of its lifecycle, the focus will increasingly shift toward consolidating its achievements, validating results, and ensuring the long-term uptake of its outputs. This includes advancing policy development in line with the insights from the PESTEL analysis, promoting sustainable collaboration between civil and defence stakeholders, and reinforcing the EU's cybersecurity leadership on the global stage.

The final version of this report, due at Month 24, will build on the current progress by providing an in-depth impact analysis, including a review of community engagement metrics, policy uptake, and the long-term sustainability of project outcomes. It will serve as a report capturing the full impact on and of the COcyber Community.

9 Annex

Table 2: COcyber Community – Distribution of stakeholder group per country

Country	Academia and Research Institutions	Cybersecurity professional	Defence representative	Policymakers	SMEs and Civil Society	Grand Total
Ukraine					2	2
UK	3	1			6	10
Switzerland	1	1			1	3
Sweden	1	1		1		3
Spain	11	3		1	5	20
Slovenia	1			1	1	3
Slovakia		1		2	2	5
Romania		1	1	3	1	6
Portugal	3					3
Poland	2	1		1	3	7
Norway	3			2	1	6
Netherlands		3			4	7
Malta		1		1		2
Luxembourg		1		1	1	3
Lithuania					2	2
Latvia				1	1	2
Italy	3	1	1	3	13	21
Ireland	2	3		1	1	7
Hungary		1		1		2
Greece	2	6	1	1	5	15
Germany	4	1		1	7	13
France	1	2	1	4	7	15
Finland	3	1		2		6
Estonia	2			5	1	8
Egypt	1					1
Denmark	2		1		1	4
Czech Republic		1	1	2		4

Cyprus					1	1
Croatia				2		2
Bulgaria				3		3
Belgium	4	11	4	16	38	73
Austria	2			1	2	5
Grand Total	51	40	10	56	106	263